

SIL

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Society of Limnology

news

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Science meets Art: panels showing data from seven lakes from seven continents. From left to right: Lake Tovel, Italy; Lake Vanda, Antarctica; Lake Baikal, Russia; El Morado Proglacial Lake, Chile; Lakes Mendota, Menona, and Wingra, USA; Lake Hillier, Australia; Lake Abiyata, Ethiopia. Photo by Alice Hargrave.

the President

Dear SIL members,

Where were you in early August 2022? I hope you took the opportunity to participate in the centennial Congress of SIL in Berlin, whether in person or remotely connected. From my perspective, this Congress was a huge success, worthy of the long scientific and social tradition that our society has accumulated over the last century. From the situation when limnology was still a young and largely undefined discipline in 1922, towards today when limnology is at the core of freshwater research and management world-wide, SIL has always been a part of this international endeavor. I think we all can be proud of being part of such a traditional, international scientific society. I would like to thank again our colleagues Rita Adrian, Mark Gessner and Lars Tranvik from the Local Organizing Committee, and the Professional Conference Organizer K.I.T. who managed to run this big, international event. The first preliminary agreements to organize the centennial conference in Berlin were taken during the SIL conference in Budapest in 2013 – it is very obvious that optimism and endurance are needed to transform such an idea into reality. And we can particularly be happy that despite the ongoing COVID-19 situation, so many of our colleagues decided to come to Berlin so that we could celebrate the centennial in person – with stimulating keynote lectures, numerous well-thought scientific talks and poster presentations, and a lot of social interactions.

“What SIL stands for and how SIL is perceived depends largely on you, the SIL members.”

But tradition is not enough to justify the existence and persistency of associations. What SIL stands for and how SIL is perceived depends largely on you, the SIL members. We have re-arranged our previous International Committee of National Representatives into the group of SIL-Ambassadors, to foster the exchange and interaction with the limnological communities and national associations in a more intense way that we have achieved so far. But please keep in mind that all of you, the SIL-members, are ambassadors of our society. To keep SIL vibrant, interest and engagement are welcome, at all levels of our society. When talking about tradition versus being prepared for the future, a giveaway hint for proper consideration of the challenges ahead is the participation of young limnologists in the Congress. I was deeply impressed

that so many of the participants were students and early-career researchers, and I hope that many of them enjoyed the meeting and decided to become part of this international community of limnologists. SIL needs young, diverse members from all over the world, to realize its mission and vision. A wonderful reflection of the enormous impact of young limnologists on the appearance of our society is the work of the SIL board, which is now dominated by young Vice Presidents and early-career representatives. I am convinced that you all appreciate the recent modernization of many structures and processes within SIL, contributed by our young board members.

Shifts in board composition also mean that previous members leave the board. We express our deepest gratitude to Tamar Zohary who has been the face of SIL as its General Secretary and Treasurer for nine years. Very few people have done so much as Tamar to run SIL through difficult times. I am very happy and proud that I could work with her during the last four years, and I hope you all join me when wishing Tamar enjoyable and relaxed days during her retirement. But please also join me in welcoming our newly elected General Secretary and Treasurer, Björn Wissel, who has replaced Tamar and now will steer a large part of the everyday work to run the society.

Not surprisingly, the preparation of the next SIL Congress has started. During the Closing Ceremony in Berlin, Luciana Gomez-Barbosa introduced the location where we will meet in May 2024 – Foz do Iguaçu in Brazil, close to the borders of Argentina and Paraguay, and next to the famous Iguacu waterfalls. I find it very promising that we will meet once again in South America, after almost 30 years since the last SIL meeting in Sao Paulo in 1995. Central and South America is a region where limnologists are very active and contribute substantially to resolving environmental challenges. I am confident that the Local Organization Committee will develop a program that reflects how limnologists are involved in research and management of freshwater systems, and how our international community can contribute by interaction and collaboration. Please reserve the slot in your calendar!

Thomas Mehner
SIL President

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In this issue SIL's President T. Mehner has written a news-filled letter and we have some great feedback from SIL100-Berlin. News from SIL's mentorship program and comments from the Brian Moss Award winners highlight SIL's dedication to its younger members, while we also learn about SIL's long history of limnological publications. Two of SIL's Working Groups have contributed reports of their activities and this issue's Opinion article outlines a global approach to lake restoration. From the Limnology Around the World section, we can learn more about cyanobacterial control in Brazil, a limnological station in Poland's lake district and turning science into art from the United States. Please meet four of our members in the FACES of SIL section. Unfortunately, we have lost another outstanding limnologist, Brian R. Allanson.

Hope you enjoy this issue of SILnews.

Giovanna Flaim,
Editor SILnews

Contribution deadline for the July 2023 issue:
01 April, 2023
Send to: SILnews Editor, Giovanna Flaim, at
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SIL 100
BERLIN | GERMANY

36th Congress of the
International Society of Limnology
7 – 10 August 2022 | www.sil2022.org

A look back on a *Wonderful* Congress

a: The Co-chairs during the opening ceremony b: The Classic Quartet enriched by a 'clarinet' making it a quintet. c: Thomas Mehner, president of SIL, cutting SIL's birthday cake.

SIL 100 – the centennial and 36th Congress of SIL – held in Berlin, Germany, from 7 to 10 August 2022, was a great success. Participants entered into personal exchange, the atmosphere was stimulating, facilitated by the positive spirit of the participants, the high quality of contributions in the individual scientific sessions, and interesting presentations by the seven plenary speakers, including the Baldi and Kilham lecturers. Importantly, there was a good mix of age groups. More than a third of the registered participants were early career scientists, suggesting the society is rejuvenating. Considering the ongoing constraints imposed by the COVID-19 pandemic and the war in Ukraine, the number of onsite registrations greatly exceeded expectations. Unfortunately, however, various countries where limnology is traditionally well-developed were less well represented and there were also late cancellations by delegates due to visa issues and travel restrictions.

The **opening ceremony** was an excellent start into the Congress. It generated a lasting, friendly and open-minded atmosphere for the SIL centennial, reminiscent of the Swedish-German tradition of the founders Einar Naumann and August Thienemann. Welcome addresses were given by the Swedish ambassador to Germany Per Thöresson, the president of the German Limnological Society Markus Weiterer, and the director of the Leibniz Institute of Freshwater Ecology and Inland Fisheries, the host institute, Luc De Meester. Presidential keynotes were given by SIL president Thomas Mehner (Diversity of researcher types and plurality of philosophical concepts in limnology) and former president Gene Likens (Some reflections on 6 decades of international limnology). These presentations were accompanied with live music performed by the Classic Quartet, enriched by a clarinetist, who played water themes from both Swedish (Vattenringar by Dan Gisen Malmquist) and German composers (Wassermusik by Georg Friedrich Händel).

Several new aspects were introduced at SIL100, which contributed to the success of the Congress. In particular, the **scientific program**, developed by the limnological community, was **entirely bottom up**. Instead of predefined topics, all sessions built on ideas submitted by session conveners. This resulted in a total of 41 sessions spanning a variety of themes that covered curiosity-driven fundamental limnological research as much as practical issues relating to urgently needed advice on the protection and management of freshwaters.

There was no printed material except for a small **pocket program** for quick orientation, providing essential information needed during the Congress. This succinct format was well received by the participants. In addition, a **Congress app** helped participants navigate the detailed program. The app allowed participants to search for events, compile individual schedules, and make announcements during the Congress using daily push notes. Participants on site were overall pleased with the functionality of the app, despite room for further improvement.

The format of the **ePoster session** was another novelty. A total of 180 ePosters presented by participants on site were grouped within six overarching session topics that were each assigned to one of six big screens during a two-hour evening poster session. Unfortunately, the six screens proved insufficient for the number of attendees present. More screens and more space would have been needed, which would have incurred additional costs. On the positive side, the ePosters were available throughout the Congress on all screens, both at the venue and remotely, and the onsite participants made use of this opportunity. In conclusion, ePosters clearly have a value, but if they are considered for future SIL Congresses, the specific format requires improvement.

Impressions from the poster session.

Impressions atmosphere at the Limnology Night.

A unique novelty was a **gift for the plenary speakers**. The special occasion of the Centennial called for a **special souvenir**: a colourful specimen of a **Buddy Bear** - a Berlin landmark that symbolizes cultural diversity and peaceful coexistence.

At last, the Congress dinner, traditionally a fairly formal event, was conceived

Plenary speaker Nancy Grimm and her Berlin Buddy Bear.

this time as an informal **Limnology Night** in the open-air atmosphere of a Berlin beer garden. As many as 330 limnologists enjoyed beer and the barbecue during a wonderful summer night, accompanied by the Keller Blues Band featuring SIL president Thomas Mehner on bass.

SIL 100 in numbers

SIL 100 in Berlin was organized as a **Hybrid Congress**. A total of 626 scientists from 49 countries attended the Congress, not including exhibitors, guests, accompanying persons, and others. This number greatly exceeded the expectations we had in view of the restrictions and uncertainties related to the COVID-19 pandemic and the ongoing war in Ukraine. Conversely, online attendees were fewer than expected, totalling 230 registrations, which may reflect not only the great interest in direct personal interactions after nearly two years of isolation, but also that online participation is still not considered a satisfactory alternative. More than one third of the participants were early career scientists, indicating their strong interest to participate in person.

Fig 1: Participants per country represented by (a) ≥ 10 participants and (b) < 10

participants. Countries with < 10 participants included Bolivia, Columbia, Iceland, Indonesia, Iran, Lithuania, Malaysia, Peru, Uzbekistan, Armenia, Bulgaria, Chile, Croatia, Ecuador, Ethiopia, Kazakhstan, Latvia, Russia, Slovenia, South Africa, India, Singapore, Uruguay, Greece, Philippines, Serbia, Ukraine, Norway, Argentina, Estonia, Romania, Turkey, New Zealand, Denmark, Portugal, Finland, Ireland (countries are depicted in clockwise order).

The percentage of onsite participation was highest for attendees from Germany.

Impressions at the venue during the opening session.

In general, it was also high for representatives from other European countries, North America and Japan (Fig. 1a). The Congress was unusual in marking SIL's centennial, and also in taking place under the influence of a pandemic and a war. Hence, it may not reflect longer-term trends in participation.

The plenary presentations were live-streamed, along with three ordinary sessions scheduled in the plenary hall. Presentations in the other six session rooms were also systematically recorded and posted in the **eLibrary on the Congress OPADE platform** for later views till 3 months after the Congress. Further, all ePosters and oral on-demand presentations (*i.e.* 10-minute pre-recorded presentations not scheduled in the onsite program) were posted in the Congress eLibrary for general availability both during and after the Congress. The technical requirements for recordings and particularly the live-streaming in the plenary hall incurred substantial costs, similar in magnitude to the costs for the room rentals in the Congress venue.

SIL 100 - a Semi Hybrid Congress

We could accommodate 700 onsite participants at the venue and expected an additional 800 online. While the number of participants onsite was close to the maximum capacity, we had greatly overestimated the number of online participants. Only 228 registered. This suggests that costs for online attendance were considered too high or that the appeal of online attendance was limited, possibly because only part of the program was live-streamed, because participants were keen on meeting in person after more than two years of travel constraints, or that online formats had reached a saturation point. The future will show whether well-conceived online formats can boost registration for remote attendance once the travel situation has normalized again.

The **Plenary Lectures** had an average of 71 online viewers, for a total of about 500. This number includes the Kilham and Baldi lectures. The number of

online participants per plenary corresponded to an average of 31% of online registrations. This was an unexpectedly low fraction, especially when considering that the plenaries were all scheduled in the early afternoon local time (CEST) in order to facilitate remote participants from east and west nearly around the globe to follow the presentations live either in the morning or in the evening.

The three **live streamed** sessions in the plenary hall attracted an average of 72 online participants, about the same as the plenaries, suggesting attendance by broadly the same scientists. This average online attendance is also similar to the number of onsite participants in other session rooms, which could accommodate between 80 and 120 participants. This outcome speaks in favor of the hybrid format for scientific sessions. It must be noted, however, that these sessions in the plenary hall were the only ones accessible online in real time, so that they had no competition from parallel sessions. This underlines again that even among the relatively few online attendees, less than a third regularly took advantage of live streaming.

The **number of visits on the OPADE Congress platform** between 1 and 25 August 2022 (6 days prior and 15 days after the Congress) were high several days prior (around 200 visits), peaked during the Congress (237-331 visits) and levelled off thereafter (from 117 the day after the Congress to 4 visits 15 days later). The participants clearly sought information on the platform primarily before and during the Congress, whereas demand rapidly declined thereafter. Until two weeks after the Congress, the **eLibrary** (ePosters and oral on-demand recordings) had a total of 3819 visits and an average time spent per presentation of 2:43 minutes. The **top 10 ePosters** were visited 41-73 times – for about 1.5 minutes. The **top 10 oral on-demand presentations** were visited 15-135 times for about 2.5 minutes.

Japanese Delegation: Yasuyuki FUJII (PhD student), Mayu KIMITUKI (17, high school student), Riku MORIMOTO (14, junior high school student) and Marina HATA (University student).

Overall, live-streaming from the plenary hall and other hybrid features of the Congress were not commensurate with the organizational demands and financial costs that these digital features incurred. This holds for the plenaries, eLibrary and chats, and somewhat less so for the ordinary sessions in the plenary hall. As SIL100 has shown, returning to physical meetings is attractive. However, as online and hybrid conferences have started to proliferate as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic, further developing online formats that partly or fully replace physical meetings would appear to be a necessary consideration also for SIL, not least to reduce the environmental footprint of international congresses that require long-distance travel.

In conclusion, various novelties were introduced for the centennial, partly due to constraints imposed by the COVID-19 pandemic and partly because of sustainability considerations. Most of them enriched the Congress and would be worth considering for future SIL Congresses, the next one of which will take place in Brazil in August 2024. A complete hybrid format would be desirable to live up to SIL's aspiration to involve limnologists from around the world in the face of financial or other constraints to attending in person, and, importantly, to reduce the environmental impact of the Congresses. As digital communication technologies are further evolving, costs for fully fledged, high-quality hybrid congresses could substantially drop in the future. SIL should be prepared to seize such opportunities to organize future congresses that are even more inclusive than in the past 100 years. Einar Naumann and August Thienemann would be pleased.

Rita Adrian, Mark Gessner, Lars Tranvik, Sami Domisch, Emma Kritzberg, Florian Leese, Markus Weitere, Ryan Sponseller

The **minutes for SIL2022 congress meetings and activities** (Executive board meeting, Global Outreach Committee meeting, SIL General Assembly, and Student Awards/Closing Ceremony) are available to read and download on our website, under the [past congresses tab](#).

SIL's Mentorship Program (SMP)

The SMP offers students and early careers limnologists from countries with developing economies a chance to be mentored by experienced scientists within SIL's international community. During the SIL2022 Workshop we presented feedback of the ongoing SMP where eleven mentor-mentee dyads from 15 countries were involved.

The goals of the SMP program are to contribute to capacity building and knowledge transfer in developing countries by encouraging and supporting young limnology researchers. In this way, SIL fosters international collaborations by increasing networks where members are engaged in a dynamic limnological community.

The call for applications for the SMP is permanently opened for mentors and mentees. Mentees must be ECRs or Master/PhD students affiliated with a limnological research institution in a developing country. They need to indicate their study discipline, research field and which water bodies they are focusing on, among other information. Mentors must be SIL members or be willing to become a SIL member and be an academic or governmental researcher in limnology or a related field, and holding a PhD for at least 5 years. Also, they need to be interested in supporting researchers from developing countries, and thus be financially capable of paying SIL fees for the mentee. The mentors joining the programme will guide and advise the mentees for up to three years. All this information is detailed on [SIL's webpage](#).

The SMP coordination team tries to make the best possible matches when arranging mentor-mentee dyads. The initial stage of the SMP starts with a mentor-mentee agreement, where the parties jointly indicate their goals by defining areas and topics where the mentee needs support from the mentor. This support also includes soft skills such as writing an article, a CV or improve networking. They must also state mutual agreements on their responsibilities, the timeline of their working plan and the expected outcomes. Since launching the SMP in January 2021, twelve dyads have been established with mentees from Peru, Argentina, Brazil, Mexico, Madagascar, Ethiopia and the Philippines, and mentors from Canada, USA, Denmark, Germany, Spain, Greece and Italy. In order to assess the development of the SMP, in July 2022 the SMP coordination team sent a feedback questionnaire to dyads participating in the SMP for 12-18 months. Everyone responded, and the results were presented in the virtual Mentorship Workshop held during the SIL2022 in Berlin.

Most mentees showed high satisfaction by the benefits they encountered. Namely, an opportunity to discuss the focus of their careers and the results of their research; effective guidance to apply new and adequate methodologies and to prepare their thesis and articles or conference presentations; make new connections; expand their networks; learn to review papers; obtain post-doc positions and also become a member of SIL and have inspiring conversations.

Students and ECRs from developing countries had a positive experience. We really thank all mentors for their incredible work! Student participants in the workshop expressed their willingness to join the SMP, welcome! Students even suggested that the SMP should be extended to all countries.

We learned a lot during these 18 months and we look forward to improve and enlarge the SMP with the proposals discussed in the workshop. Among

the ideas that emerged are planning a more effective platform with data from potential mentors and mentees to facilitate matches, a blog for mentees, initial explicative conversations with participants, higher availability of coordinators and regular feedback processes.

We invite all limnologists to participate by filling in the application forms for mentors and mentees on the SIL webpage. If you need more information do not hesitate to write to Inés O'Farrell (bioinesofarrell@gmail.com) or Michelle Gros (Business@limnology.org).

Testimonies

2022 SIL Berlin meeting: Mentor, Nelson Hairston (a) could not attend the meeting but introduced by e-mail (b) Mentee, Laura Saures (right) to his colleague, Roxanne Razavi (left, Asst. Prof. at SUNY-ESF) suggesting they meet up at the conference since they have similar research interests. They sent Nelson this selfie from the opening assembly where by chance they happened to sit close to each other.

Mentee Laura Melo Vieira Soares (Brazil): We discussed scientific aspects of my current research and mostly he provided me with generous and valuable professional advice. He has enthusiastically supported my scientific development by providing feedback on presentations and revision of a manuscript proposal. In addition, he has supported my overall career advancement by (a) helping me to expand my network introducing me to other limnological researchers; (b) encouraging me to attend professional meetings; (c) sharing position advertisement, making a connection with colleagues about funding possibilities and opportunities of visiting their labs, and spreading my CV. Finally, during all the interactions we had, he enthusiastically helped me with his experience.

Mentor Nelson G. Hairston (USA): I found it a positive and rewarding experience for me as a mentor. The mentee chosen for me is smart, friendly and collaborative. She had already achieved some nice successes in publishing interesting research. I believe that we found ways that my mentoring could be helpful.

The Brian Moss Student Competition

Impressions from the Congress

1st place winner, SIL student competition 2022

SAMUEL DIJOUX CZECHIA

SIL Berlin Congress: a congress between two centuries. The 36th congress organized last summer by the International Society of Limnology in Berlin was my fresh introduction to the society and to the vaster world of limnologists from across the world. Overall, this conference had been a thrilling experience for me and an awesome opportunity to meet and network with new people. I was particularly happy to have been present to celebrate the 100th year of existence of the Society.

Celebrating such a milestone in one of the most historical-loaded cities of the 20th century undeniably represented an important pivotal moment for the Society. This congress was an excellent opportunity to merge SIL history with the current and emerging concerns of limnologists in order to engage future generations of researchers in studying and protecting inland waters. They addressed such challenges through multiple aspects. They traced back the society's history and the knowledge gathered by limnologists over the past century until today (see the *100 years of SIL in a nutshell*, published on sutori.com). The wide selection of posters and talks

organized in multiple parallel sessions provided the most influential and latest trends of research made across limnology fields. All keynote speakers were inspiring as they addressed future possible guidelines through their respective research domains: Nancy B. Grimm on the resilience of freshwater ecosystems to increasing disturbances; Amy Rosemond on the underlying mechanisms of global changes through spatial- and time-scale experiments; Christiane Zarfl on the impacts of anthropological pressures on river ecosystems through the linkage of observation and modelling approaches; Tamlin Pavelsky on the uses of close- to the most remote sensing approaches to tackle the influences of climate changes on aquatic systems; and Spencer R. Hall on the emerging theoretical framework for host and parasites interactions in freshwater ecosystems. One striking moment for me was the *100 limnological questions* session in which limnologists were asked to project themselves in the future and raise the plausible issues for the society to maintain and assure the protection of inland waters. This highlighted how limnologists from all over the world share the same devotion and concerns regarding the future and how much they are willing to address these questions together and to engage the public.

Last but not least, receiving the winning award of the 4th *SIL Student competition*, newly renamed after the eminent Brian Moss, for my first publication was the culminating point of the conference for me. I feel extremely humble and grateful for all the consideration my research received. The plenary talk I gave was my greatest professional experience so far. It was an overwhelming and exciting moment to be on this big stage, and I hope it was as inspiring for other early-career scientists as I had been by all the talks given during the week.

So, I would like to tip my hat to all the organizing and committee members for all the energy that went through this amazing conference, but also for their devotion that keep the SIL boat in good shape and floating. May the society pursue another century with new fresh cruise members that will handle the boat's navigation through uncertain waters.

2nd place winner, SIL student competition 2022

JOACHIM JANSEN SWEDEN

Impressions from the conference: First of all, I would like to extend a word of thanks to Judit Padisak, Tamar Zohary and the members of the judging committee for facilitating this award. I would also like to extend my gratitude to two mentors without whom the paper would not have been possible. Patrick Crill, who recently retired from Stockholm University, and Sally MacIntyre from UCSB, who gave the Baldi memorial lecture in 2018 and was awarded the Naumann-Thienemann Medal this year for her outstanding contributions to our field, but could not be here in person.

This is my first SIL conference, and I have thoroughly enjoyed it. It was a good to meet so many new and familiar colleagues and share the joy of thinking together. The following is my personal impression of the conference and some of the experiences that stood out to me.

We started on Sunday with inspiring talks from distinguished speakers, and beautiful music. Personal highlights were our president, Thomas Mehner's talk about how our background can infuse our work, and provides a unique perspective, as exemplified by the founders of our society. And Gene Likens, looking forward at the future of our field: big data, remote sensing, genomics. Both perspectives for me resonated through the following three days. Particularly memorable was Tuesday's plenary talk by Amy Rosemond about the value of surprise as a reflection of our scientific and societal beliefs. One of the advantages of being an early career researcher is that you get to be surprised a lot. The diversity of the talks, posters and workshops offered many opportunities to learn new things. Two aspects that stood out to me were how much integration there already is between field observations, remote sensing and modelling, but also how much work there is still to do in our field, in terms of gender equality and social justice, and the application of our knowledge to achieve the sustainable development goals.

To early-career researchers, conferences can be defining moments in their career, whether it is for networking or new ideas, or motivation. So it is important that they are organized well. I think this conference was organized very well. It was large enough to meet new people and expand your network, but small enough to find a common ground. And being in Berlin, the mingling was aided much by the excellence of the beer(s).

I would like to close with a word of thanks, to the conference organizers, the leadership of our esteemed society, the session chairs, and to all who attended virtually and in person.

Brian Moss Student Competition

3rd place winner, SIL student competition 2022

LENA SCHALLENBERG NEW ZEALAND

Hello fellow limnologists! Wow, what an honour and surprise to be awarded this prize and have the opportunity to attend my first SIL congress. I received the news while shaking off the Covid cobwebs on a 3-month van trip around North America, so it was exciting for many reasons, including the thought of regular showers for a few days - bliss. After two years of pandemic-induced uncertainty and isolation, it was great to be able to gather and meet face to face. As helpful as zoom can be, it just doesn't allow for the kind of relationship building and networking that in-person conferences do, so thank you to all who made it! I would like to thank my co-authors Susie Wood, Carolyn Burns and John Pearman for their help with the manuscript, and the student competition organizers and judges for all of their work. I also extend a special thanks to Joyce Moss for her generous donation to what will now be the Brian Moss Student Competition. With this new name and new energy, I also highly recommend that SIL students everywhere put a paper forward for this award!

The SIL100 congress was a whirlwind of a time with so many interesting talks, board/committee meetings and putting faces to the names of many brilliant limnologists from around the world. I was especially excited to be able to present my PhD work to scientists from a range of countries I wouldn't normally have the privilege of, thanks to SIL's international reach. This gave me some interesting ideas for future research directions, and I want to thank those of you who came to me with an interest in picocyanobacteria! As COVID restrictions continue to ease, I hope to see many more countries represented at the 2024 congress in Brazil so we can all continue to expand our networks and broaden our collaborations. Recently I also joined the SIL executive board as an ECR Global Outreach, I am happy to report that we are now actively working to improve communication and networking between limnologists from around the globe, particularly previously underrepresented nations and regions. Let's continue to grow, promote and celebrate the diversity of our truly global society! I will also sneakily use this as a little plug to please get in touch with Zeynep (the new and wonderful VP Global Outreach) or myself if you have any fresh ideas or want to be involved in our Global Outreach Committee- we welcome all discussions! Thanks again to everyone and have a great new year.

Unfortunately, **Marcin Dziuba, Poland** - the joint 3rd place winner was not able to attend the Berlin Congress.

Sponsor of the Brian Moss Student Competition

JOYCE MOSS

As my taxi from the airport drew up outside Hotel Berlin, I was immediately struck by the animated voices of the crowd of delegates to the SIL 2022 congress gathered, as they were, in clusters on the pavement in front of the hotel. Inside, the feeling of energy permeating the air continued – as it did for the all the days of the congress: people hurrying from one lecture venue to another, being busy on computers in 'rest' areas, talking and exchanging views, a general 'buzz' in the air and a friendly informality. I enjoyed listening to numerous lectures, and the atmosphere of the congress conveyed the wonderful opportunity it was for limnologists at different stages of their careers and from different parts of the world to meet and exchange ideas and make contacts with others. It was my personal pleasure to meet both old friends and new – people whose names were familiar to me, because Brian had talked of them, but whom I had not met before. I can now put faces to the memories, and some of those new-found friends related anecdotes about Brian that I found both amusing and rather charming, and which I took home and will remember in the future (like his getting lost cross-country skiing in the dark in Canada before the age of mobile phones. I do not remember his telling me that himself!). The friendliness and humanity of SIL struck me forcefully, as did the vigour of the scientific exchanges.

Brian in Quebec. Photo by Joyce Moss

Everyone involved with the organisation of the Berlin Congress deserves our thanks and congratulations on making it such a success. Brian was passionate about SIL and its future. He would have been elated with the energy of the 2022 Congress.

SIL – 100 years of Publishing

Jack Jones published a curated collection of our 100-year history of published work entitled “A century of scholarship archived in the *Verhandlungen*, *Mitteilungen*, and *Inland Waters*: publications of the International Society of Limnology” (2022, *Inland Waters*,

<https://doi.org/10.1080/20442041.2022.2104591>). It’s an abridged content review drawn from the three SIL publications that document the discoveries of our predecessors and contemporaries. There are 30 volumes of the *Verhandlungen* (*Proceedings, 1922–2010*), containing some 7780 manuscripts, which archive findings presented at the Congresses. The practice was to present an oral presentation and deposit a manuscript with the editor for publication. The collection tracks developments and discoveries over time and across the globe. Early volumes typically contained about 40 manuscripts with a peak of 850 submissions from the Congress in Ireland (1998). Most are short articles of under 2000 words, with additional space allocated to the plenary presentations. Numerous papers have been cited between 50 and 650 times.

These contributions serve as time-capsule syntheses of major topics in the discipline. The *Mitteilungen* (Communications, 1953–1996) includes 278 contributions, some quite lengthy; it began with dedicated articles on

analytical and field techniques, then broadened to include collections on focal topics such as microbiology, tropical ecology, African lakes, algal dynamics and caloric equivalents for calculating ecological energetics. A Jubilee Symposium (*Mitteilungen*, Vol. 20) provided an interesting synopsis of the first 50 years of SIL scholarship. *Inland Waters* was launched at the 31st Congress in South Africa (2010). It is the peer-reviewed, scholarly outlet for original papers within the framework of SIL and currently includes over 500 publications, with an impact factor of 3 (2011 and ongoing). The synthesis is based on 160 articles (out of 8600) with republication of 15 articles from the collection, spanning 1953–2022, to further illustrate the scope of this collective body of work.

Manuscripts from the *Verhandlungen* and *Mitteilungen* have been scanned and are easily searchable, which provides ready access to past findings. The presidential addresses include interesting details about the founding of the Society and interesting bits of information such as phosphorus was considered a trace element in the 1930s and that an important paper on eutrophication in Swiss lakes resulted in the removal of phosphorus from detergents in Canada. More than one meta-analysis is contained in this impressive body of information. It seems a look into past discoveries will inform the future.

Lago di Muzzano – Switzerland. Photo by Miquel Lürling

SIL Working Group Updates

LAKE RESTORATION WG

This WG was conceived during SIL2016 (Torino) where all attendees of special session 40 on Lake Restoration (19 oral presentations, 8 posters) expressed, during a meeting afterwards, that finding common ground and exchanging experiences would be most welcome. The WG tries to accommodate this via organizing special sessions at conferences (e.g. SEFS 2017, SIL 2018), by contributions at international conferences (e.g. NALMS, ASLO, Lahti Lakes), by co-organizing symposia such as [Lahti Lakes 2021](#), by hosting special issues and posts on social media. The WG hosts a Facebook account ([Lake Restoration Research](#)) and a twitter account ([@SilWorking](#)). Colleagues working on lake restoration are encouraged to include #LakeRestoration in posts.

The first real WG special issue “Toward Preventative Management in Lakes” appeared in *Inland Waters*, volume 12(1), 8 April 2022. The importance of the special issue was underpinned at SIL2022 where the publisher notified that 5 of the 10 most downloaded papers in 2022 stemmed from this special issue. Ideas, suggestions, initiatives for a special issue are most welcome.

The WG had its regular household meeting at SIL2022 (Berlin). A history of WG activities was presented, the recent WG special issue highlighted, its affiliation to the [UNEP World Water Quality Alliance Ecosystems Workstream](#) explained, and the way forward was discussed.

The WWQA Ecosystems Workstream was established in 2021 to support large-scale restoration initiatives to prevent, halt and redress the destruction of our freshwater ecosystems, focusing initially on water quality management in lakes and their catchments. It is currently building the WWQA Ecosystems Membership, reviewing and synthesising their experiences on the challenges and benefits of lake restoration. It is enhancing coordination of action in the area of lake restoration and mobilization of policymakers and raising awareness across sectors of the multiple benefits of effective sustainability-based restoration of freshwater ecosystems. The WWQA hosted two sessions at the SIWI World International Water Week 2021 [Investing for Change through the WWQA](#) August 24th 2021. The sessions can be found at [Investing for change through the World Water Quality Alliance – YouTube](#) for August 24th and for August 26th 2021. The sessions had 254 registrations from all over the globe and received the SIWI Gold Standard for Diversity.

Another activity is the [GLOBAL SURVEY OF LAKE](#)

[RESTORATION IN PRACTICE](#). This survey aims to compile experiences gained from real restoration of lakes in order to identify the leading causes for failure/success of lake restoration and to draw recommendations for future initiatives. The survey is available in 5 languages, is still open and before SIL2022 had already received 179 answers from 64 countries. Yet, any additional answer is most welcome. [You can access the survey here](#).

There was quite some consensus on the WG joining the WWQA. The WWQA offers direct input to UNEP and to the UNEA process, it is a broad bottom-up initiative with lots of momentum and the means to bring the importance of good water quality on the agenda of policy makers. The attendees further discussed the water quality

challenges related to current and coming pressures. Holistic approaches in preventing and restoring inland waters are needed which underscores the importance of including other disciplines as well as those who can transfer knowledge to policy makers. Throughout the congress “management”, “restoration”, “protection” of inland waters was brought forward and also the majority of the “100 important questions for limnology” mentioned these. The WG on Lake Restoration is in the epic center of these current water quality challenges. The knowledge within the WG and the network it has, might offer a valuable start for colleagues confronted with real time water quality issues in lakes, ponds and reservoirs that were brought forward during the conference in Berlin.

The WG on Lake Restoration appreciates feedback and especially initiatives and suggestions for special sessions, small focused meetings (online/in person), special issues, opinion papers, enhancement of visibility, exchange of information are welcomed highly.

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Treatment of Lake Kralingse Plas - Rotterdam, The Netherlands with a phosphate binder (Nov 2021).
Photo by Miquel Lürling

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LIMNOLOGY OF DRYLANDS WG

International Network on Limnology of Drylands (INLD)

Website: www.inld.pro.br | Twitter: [@inld_limnology](https://twitter.com/inld_limnology) | Instagram: [@inld.limnology](https://www.instagram.com/inld.limnology)

Currently, climate change and the human-domain are the main drivers of changes in aquatic ecosystems across the world. In anthropogenic scenarios, warmer climates, overexploitation, nutrients enrichment and other drivers may induce irreversible shifts in these ecosystems, mainly in dry zones. Aquatic ecosystems have a great ecological and economic relevance in arid and semiarid zones, useful for irrigation and other economic activities, essential to the livelihood of 2.1 billion people (Reid *et al.*, 2005. Millennium Ecosystem Assessment. UNEP).

Since its creation, the greatest challenge of the International Network on Limnology of Drylands (INLD) is the reconciliation of conservation and sustainable development of these zones. During the last decade, extreme and prolonged droughts arising as one of the main consequences of anthropogenic climate change (Marvel *et al.*, 2019. Nature 569: 59-65) have negatively influenced the biodiversity and resilience of water bodies. Therefore, research and experiments will be carried out aiming to understand the effects of local stressors and consequences of increasing temperature on these ecosystems.

Group Meeting had a special focus on the actions developed between 2020 and 2021 (Fig. 1b). Among the proposals for future actions, researchers highlighted the importance of establishing a common field protocol to be used by the members in all countries, mainly in lentic ecosystems. Colleagues from Brazil, Spain, Egypt, Denmark, Germany, Ecuador, Russia, India, among others, were present. The protocol is being prepared and is strictly associated with the main objectives of INLD: i) to assess the current state of biological diversity in dryland aquatic ecosystems; ii) to evaluate multiple environmental stressors; iii) to develop predictive models to estimate the effects of global changes on drylands. The expectation is to answer the main threats associated with biodiversity in drylands.

Currently, the main projects of INLD prioritize the study of local pressures and global warming and their potential effects on aquatic biodiversity and water quality, including scientometric and meta-analysis studies in global dryland freshwater ecosystems, aiming to identify trends in temporal and spatial scales. Other projects underway have a special focus on a *space for time* approach: i) Galapagos program: Iconic Galapagos aquatic ecosystems as a climate change hot-spot? (Fig. 1c, e), ii) Rockpools (and temporary ecosystems) in world drylands (Fig. 1d, f), iii) Phosphorus cycling in aquatic ecosystems in drylands regions.

Fig. 1 a) Eduardo Vicente (University of Valencia) and Luciana Barbosa (Chair of INLD); b) Special Session “Ecology and conservation of temporary aquatic ecosystems” in the 36th Congress of the International Society of Limnology (SIL2022); c) El Junco lake (Galapagos National Park, San Cristobal Island); d) Rock pools (Northeast of Brazil); e) Sampling in Galapagos lakes with Miriam Steinitz- Kannan, José Carlos Lopez (Co-chair of INLD) and Raúl Tomalá; f) Arch Lagoon, a temporary lake in the Namib desert (Angola).

Regarding the activities of this WG, in 2021 and 2022 some actions were carried out in Brazil, Portugal, Spain, Germany and Ecuador. In the 2nd meeting of the Iberian Ecological Society (SIBECOL) and the XXI conference of the Iberian Association of Limnology (AIL), the special session *Ecology and conservation of temporary aquatic ecosystems* was conducted by Luciana Barbosa (INLD) and Maximo Floriano Florin (University of Castilla-La Mancha, Spain). In this session presentations from Spain, Brazil and Portugal were made, with special focus on biodiversity and the potential effects of climate change and human pressures in iconic ecosystems, such as the aquatic ecosystems of Doñana State Park (Spain). Furthermore, technical visits were made in Portugal and Spain aiming to expand actions and research lines of INLD. In Evora (Portugal), discussions revolved around advances in research projects and scientific papers, associated with biodiversity and ecological redundancy as well as new perspectives in drylands zones. In Spain, the main action was strengthening partnerships with researchers from Valencia University (Fig.1a). One of our main objectives was to identify new perspectives and approaches to improve investigations in drylands zones.

During the 36th Congress of the International Society of Limnology (SIL2022) in Germany, INLD held a special session *Ecology and conservation of temporary aquatic ecosystems*, coordinated by Luciana Barbosa, Carlos López (INLD) and Rachel Stubbington (Nottingham Trent University). This session featured presentations from Brazil, Spain, India, Australia, Ecuador and the United Kingdom. The official Working

Overall, our goal is to identify trends and emphasize the vulnerability of these dynamic and highly diverse ecosystems. With this in mind, we expect to be at the forefront of combating climate change through a better comprehension of arid systems and by providing advances for the conservation of aquatic ecosystems in drylands zones.

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Opinion

Loch Leven, long term monitoring and lake restoration. Photo by Bryan Spears

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The purpose of the World Water Quality Alliance (WWQA) is to engage and unite society to protect water quality and to redress water quality deterioration, which is one of the great challenges of the 21st Century. The foundation for the WWQA was laid in the United Nations Environment Assembly (UNEA) Resolution 3/10 on Addressing water pollution to protect and restore water-related ecosystems (UNEP/EA.3/Res.10, 2017) that requested UN Environment Programme (UNEP) to develop a global water quality assessment in collaboration with UN-Water and relevant stakeholders.

As a follow-up, UNEP and the Joint Research Centre (JRC) of the European Commission launched the WWQA in Ispra, Italy, on 19 September 2019 to “bring together a wide range of expertise in fields of water quality science, technology innovation, governance and diplomacy to seek solutions”.

The WWQA embodies a voluntary, multi-stakeholder network that works as a genuine partnership, an open community of practice. The WWQA focuses on improving the quality of water around the world through monitoring, analysis, research, communication and identifying solutions for the maintenance and restoration of impaired aquatic ecosystems.

The WWQA aims to provide a participatory platform for water quality assessments, issues and solutions and invites all that can play a role in protecting and improving water quality, no matter their qualifications or expertise, to join the WWQA. To do so, an email can be sent to wwqa-coordination@un.org stating which workstream/s you would like to contribute to, a short summary of your organization and how the work your organization links to the specific workstream/s of the WWQA.

The efforts of the WWQA are currently divided into 14 active workstreams:

- Baseline World Water Quality Assessment
- GlobeWQ STI Platform development
- Africa Use Case
- Capacity Development Consortium (CDCm)
- Social Engagement Platform
- Citizen data for SDG 6.3.2
- **Ecosystems**
- Friends of Groundwater
- Global Scenarios Ecosystem Health
- Scenario Analysis for the World Water Quality Assessment
- Plastics
- Water-ForCE
- Towards a Pan-African Water Quality Program (PAWaQ)
- Youth Action for World Water Quality

WWQA ECOSYSTEMS WORKSTREAM

About WWQA Ecosystems

The WWQA Ecosystems Workstream was established in 2021 to support large-scale initiatives to prevent, halt and redress the destruction of our freshwater ecosystems, focusing initially on water quality management in lakes and their catchments. It is coordinated by IHE-Delft with a core group of the UK Centre for Ecology & Hydrology, UNEP, European Joint Research Centre, Wageningen University, and the Norwegian Institute for Water Research. Strong links have been established between the WWQA

Ecosystems team and the SIL Working Group on Lake Restoration.

The WWQA Ecosystems Workstream encourages an open membership behind a common goal: to assess and improve water quality with a focus on freshwater restoration. WWQA Ecosystems has a long-term ambition to support restoration strategies combining socio-economic and biophysical evidence to drive the transition from heavily polluting activities towards those that relieve stress on the aquatic environment. A key aim is to support sustainable management of freshwaters whilst releasing economic growth.

Recent WWQA Ecosystems Activities

The WWQA Ecosystems Workstream hosted two sessions at the 2021 SIWI World Water Week. The sessions titled ‘Investing for Change through the World Water Quality Alliance’ were held on 24th August 2021 and on 26th August 2021. The session was awarded the SIWI Gold Standard for Diversity. The session was a first step in establishing a Global Community of Practice, with 254 registrations (Chart 1) and contributions from active restoration programmes in Chile, North America, Europe, New Zealand, India, and Africa. [Links to parallel sessions can be found here.](#)

The SIWI 2021 sessions developed the Top 5 Actions required to transform lake management in the coming years:

1. Restoration must now move to embrace both ecological and social benefits.
2. National institutional capacities must be enhanced to accelerate uptake and implementation.

Fig. 1 Analytics of participation in sessions hosted by WWQA Ecosystems Workstream at the 2021 SIWI World Water Week.

3. New partnerships must be fostered to deliver better integration of policies and sectoral interests.
4. Monitoring, assessment, and future scenario projections must be embedded within restoration investments to underpin long-term evidence-based decision-making.
5. Enabling conditions must be created to de-risk and enhance investment in sustainable lake management, with an active role for new public-private partnerships.

Fig. 2 Responses from the lake management practitioner community indicating the global importance of multiple pressures. Only responses indicating ‘moderate’ or ‘severe’ impacts of pressures are listed.

The WWQA Ecosystems Workstream also organised a special session at the latest SIL conference in Berlin. The session ‘Sustainable Freshwater Management in the 21st Century’ took place on August 9th 2022 and hosted 24 oral contributions from 12 different countries.

WWQA Ecosystems through UNEP and JRC, conducted a [GLOBAL SURVEY OF LAKE RESTORATION IN PRACTICE](#) collating experiences of the lake restoration practitioner community, attracting 179 questionnaire returns with coverage from 64 countries until the SIL2022 conference. Preliminary analyses indicate that many pressures are pervasive, but that nutrients and climate change are perceived to be most important globally (Fig. 2). General messages to date include that:

- poor understanding of pressures and their effects is perceived to be one of the most important reasons behind failure in lake restoration,
- most restoration programmes do not consider future climate change in their long-term planning, and,
- novel pressures will call for new approaches to lake restoration, both in setting restoration targets and devising restoration strategies.

This survey aims to compile experiences gained from real restoration of lakes in order to identify the leading causes for failure/success of lake restoration and to draw recommendations for future initiatives. The

survey is available in 5 languages, and is still open to receive answers. To access the survey please visit the website at this address: <https://forms.office.com/r/uFnKsxLT5M>

The survey analysis will be disseminated in the scientific literature, to a wider audience, and will serve as input for a White Paper to identify key issues and implementation of actions for better coordination to protect and restore water quality in lakes.

Want to contribute to the work of WWQA Ecosystems?

The WWQA Ecosystems Core Group convenes the wider Membership, reviewing, and synthesising their experiences on the challenges and benefits of lake restoration. This wider membership helps us to identify opportunities for enhancing coordination of action in the area of lake restoration and relevant policies, and, conducting awareness raising campaigns across sectors on the multiple benefits of effective sustainability-based restoration of freshwater ecosystems.

[More information about the WWQA Ecosystems Workstream can be found at here.](#)

To express an interest in contributing to WWQA Ecosystems please send an email to:

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Reither See – Austria, Photo by Miquel Lürling

LIMNOLOGY AROUND THE WORLD: BRAZIL

Mitigation measures for controlling and managing cyanobacterial blooms in a tropical shallow urban pond in Southeast Brazil.

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Restoration of eutrophic waters is one of the main challenges of current limnology and one of the most severe environmental problems water resource managers face. The most noticeable effects of eutrophication in urban lakes worldwide are high turbidity associated with high densities of cyanobacteria, unpleasant odors, fish mortality, changes in food webs, and loss of biodiversity. These effects seriously impair the ability of urban lakes to provide essential ecosystem services (Hamilton *et al.*, 2014, Le Moal *et al.*, 2019).

Reducing eutrophication and the consequent blooms of cyanobacteria require integrated actions and strategic decisions (Lürling *et al.*, 2016). One of the most important actions is a system analysis that identifies the sources of nutrients, the primary sources of water for the system, and the dominant cyanobacterial species. Such analyses provide the insights needed to propose measures to decrease nutrient inputs, algal blooms, and, consequently, restore aquatic ecosystem services.

Cyanobacterial blooms in the pond at the Mariano Procopio Museum Park (Mapro), located in Juiz de Fora, Brazil, have been reported since early 2012, when visitors and park employees noticed changes in the color of the pond's water and dense green scum on its surface. A collaboration between the museum and the Federal University of Juiz de Fora (UFJF) was the basis for several management strategies concerning this emerging problem. Analysis of the pond's water quality in March 2012 showed high phosphorus and nitrogen concentrations, indicating intense eutrophication, with high densities of cyanobacteria (blooms). A working group formed by researchers from various educational and research institutions, in partnership with the UFJF, sought to identify the leading causes of eutrophication and cyanobacterial blooms and to test the effectiveness and applicability of geoengineering techniques to control these issues. The results of this study were published in Miranda (2017), Miranda *et al.*, (2017, 2021), and Josué *et al.*, (2019).

The Mapro Pond is a small artificial, shallow, and urban reservoir (1.1 ha surface area, 1.3 m maximum depth) created for scenic purposes in the Mariano Procópio Museum Park (Fig. 1). The pond is hypereutrophic (total phosphorus >200 mg L⁻¹), leading to regular and persistent algal blooms, mainly dominated by cyanobacteria, usually *Microcystis* spp. and sporadically *Raphidiopsis raciborskii* (formerly *Cylindrospermopsis raciborskii*). Mapro Pond is fed by rainwater, runoff from the drainage basin that covers most of the park, a perennial fountain connected to a pipe coming from an uphill water spring, and an electric well pump that pumps in groundwater and is controlled by the museum's administration. The administration also controls the single outflow to the Paraibuna River, the city's main waterway. The pond is home to some fish species, including *Cyprinus* sp. (herbivorous), *Prochilodus* sp. (detritivorous), and *Hoplias* sp. (carnivorous), turtles (*Phrynops hilarii*), swans (*Cygnus* sp.), and ducks (*Anas platyrhynchos*, *Amazonetta brasiliensis*). Herons (Ardeidae) and doves (Columbidae) spend the night on an island in the middle of the pond.

Mapro Pond is representative of a common problem in Brazil, where the absence or mismanagement of water resources and poor sanitation in urban areas promote eutrophication. To identify the leading causes of eutrophication and to obtain the most promising

Fig. 1 Map and photos of Mapro Pond in the Mariano Procopio Museum Park in the Juiz de Fora municipality. A, B, and C: Bloom of cyanobacteria in the Mapro Pond. D: Birds on the central island of the Mapro Pond.

measures to improve the water quality of Mapro Pond, a three-stage research approach was implemented (Fig. 2): 1) **system analysis** to identify the primary sources of nutrients (P and N) and the dynamics of planktonic communities in the pond; 2) **laboratory experiments** to evaluate the efficiency of the combination of coagulants and ballasts for the removal of cyanobacterial biomass and P; and 3) **mesocosm experiments** in the pond, to test the control of eutrophication based on the results of stage 2. Stages 2 and 3 evaluated the applicability of geoeengineering techniques as a fast, efficient, and low-cost alternative to dredging.

Fig. 2 Schematic diagram of the eutrophication mitigation alternative development to solve the problem of Cyanobacterial Harmful Algae Blooms (CyanoHABs) in the MAPRO Pond

System analysis

Mapro Pond was monitored monthly for two years (November 2012 to October 2014). In addition, hydrological and P balances were determined. The PClake model (Janse *et al.*, 2010) estimated the critical P loading, defined by gradual changes in water quality, alternative states, or stable regimes (*e.g.*, a clear-water state dominated by submerged plants to a turbid-water state dominated by phytoplankton). More details about this approach can be found in Miranda *et al.*, 2021.

Use of geoeengineering techniques

Removing algae from the water column using a combination of coagulants and ballast, promoting flocculation and sedimentation (Floc & Sink), is a promising geoeengineering technique to control cyanobacterial blooms (Lürling *et al.*, 2016; 2020). This approach manipulates biogeochemical processes, using materials to achieve the desired chemical and/or ecological response. Given the peculiarities of each system, the first tests were carried out in the laboratory to evaluate the most efficient combination of coagulants and ballasts (Stage 2; Miranda *et al.*, 2017). Experiments were then carried out in mesocosms to verify the efficiency of the *in situ* treatment (Miranda *et al.*, in preparation, Stage 3).

Main results in the work stages

In Stage 1, we identified that cyanobacterial blooms in the Mapro Pond were dominated by *Microcystis* spp. and sporadically by *Raphidiopsis raciborskii*. The main variables responsible for phytoplankton dynamics were related to seasonality (dry and rainy season) which alters the availability of nutrients and light. The P balance study pointed out that the waterbirds were the most significant contributor of P to the pond (Fig. 3). Most of the P that enters the water column goes into the sediment, and part of this is released back into the water column (Miranda *et al.*, 2021). Modeling results indicate that the critical P load for Mapro Pond to change from its current turbid-state to a clear-state is 8.6 mg P m⁻² d⁻¹. Scenarios of increased water flow show that decreasing residence time from 79 to 35 days would increase this critical load to 14.6 mg P m⁻² d⁻¹ (Miranda *et al.*, 2021).

In Stage 2, we observed that the best combination of coagulants and ballast for removing cyanobacterial biomass depends on the dominant species. For instance, the use of chitosan (CHI), an organic coagulant, was effective in removing the biomass of *M.aeruginosa*, however ineffective in removing the biomass of *R. raciborskii* from pond water and also had a harmful effect, promoting the release of saxitoxins (Miranda *et al.*, 2017).

Fig. 3 Annual phosphorus balance of Mapro Pond in mg m⁻² d⁻¹ and percentage (%) considering input and output.

In Stage 3, after applying the Floc & Sink technique to the mesocosms, we observed an 85% reduction in chlorophyll-a over 24h (Fig. 4). However, this biomass reduction was not maintained for long due to the resurfacing of settle flocs from ongoing photosynthesis within the flocs and entrapment of oxygen. Resurfacing of settle flocs can effectively be avoided by applying an algacide, such as hydrogen peroxide, before using the Floc & Sink technique. However, it can promote the release of toxins (Miranda *et al.*, in preparation).

The use of local red soil as ballast is as efficient as lanthanum modified bentonite (LMB) in removing cyanobacterial biomass from the water column, thereby reducing the cost of system recovery.

Considerations

The eutrophication of Mapro Pond is a case of guantrophy, with the primary P input to the pond through birds (76%). We found that the critical P-load for Mapro Pond is 8.6 mg P mg⁻² d⁻¹. Reductions in external and internal P loads must be considered along with residence time management to decrease cyanobacterial proliferation. The Floc & Sink technique is unsuitable in Mapro Pond unless preceded by an algacide such as hydrogen peroxide and unless sediment resuspending fish are removed.

Managing the eutrophication and cyanobacterial blooms in Mapro Pond will depend on integrated actions to reduce external and internal P loading and cyanobacterial biomass. For example, the Floc & Sink technique should be considered alongside managing the pond's retention time to alleviate cyanobacterial blooms.

Removing cyanobacterial blooms from eutrophic systems can be a simple process using chemicals. However, the biggest challenge is keeping the water clear without bloom recurrence for an extended period. A long-lasting recovery will rely on integrated actions, and more than one strategy can be adopted. For this, tailored solutions are required, as each system is unique.

Recommendations to management in Mapro Pond

- Assessment of pond infrastructure and feasibility of channels to redirect rainwater, thus reducing particulate matter and P inputs.
- Increasing water flow and reducing backwater areas conducive to algae growth.
- Dredging the upper sediments to decrease internal P load.
- Removal of all fish that contribute to P resuspension: *Cyprinus* sp., *Prochilodus* sp., and *Hoplias* sp.
- Installation of a water level meter.
- Implementation of a monthly water monitoring program including physical and biological variables.
- Management of the resting bird population that is the main nutrient contributor to the pond.
- Abatement of cyanobacteria using hydrogen peroxide, which has algacide properties, before removing cyanobacterial biomass by geoeengineering techniques (Floc & Sink) or removing cyanobacterial biomass.

Fig. 4 Testing combinations of coagulant (bentonite modified with lanthanum, LMB) and red soil using mesocosms in Mapro Pond (Museu Mariano Procópio, Juiz de Fora, Brazil). A: Miquel Lürling and Marcela Miranda testing the coagulant dose. B: the control mesocosm. C: Marcela Miranda dosing LMB. Panel D: a treated mesocosm.

Partner institutions

Laboratory of Aquatic Ecology (LEA) of the Federal University of Juiz de Fora (UFJF)- Logistic support for data collection and limnological analysis of Mapro Pond.

Laboratory of Toxins and Natural Products from Algae of the State University of São Paulo (USP)- Analysis of toxins (Stages 1, 2, 3).

Phytoplankton Ecology and Physiology Laboratory of the State University of Rio de Janeiro (UERJ)- Logistical and academic support (Stages 2, 3).

Environmental Quality Laboratory- LAQUA of the Federal University of Juiz de Fora (UFJF)- Logistic Support (Stage 3).

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National Institute for Space Research (INPE) Earth System Science Center- Greenhouse gas analysis and mesocosm development (Stage 3).

Fig. 5 Mesocosm working group at Mapro Pond (Museu Mariano Procópio, Juiz de Fora, Brazil, September 2016).

Collaborators

A network of collaborators contributed directly to the acquisition of data, laboratory analysis, and paper preparation.

Stage 1: Dr. Maria Carolina Soares - general coordination and idealization of Stage 1 (UFJF); Dr. Fábio Roland- logistical and intellectual support (UFJF); Gladson Marques - sampling and nutrient analysis (UFJF); Felipe Rust - fieldwork and carbon analysis (UFJF); Michaela Melo - cyanobacteria counts (UFJF); Rafael Paiva and Iollanda Josué - fieldwork and zooplankton counts (UFJF); Máira Mucci - fieldwork, phytoplankton counts, and Intellectual support (UFJF); Mariana Mello - work by Campos and Intellectual support (UFJF/ WUR); Dra. Raquel Mendonça - academic support and sediment collection (UFJF); Dr. Simone Cardoso - academic support (UFJF); Dr. Roberto Junior and Roberto Marchesini- ciliate analysis (UFJF); Dr. Haroldo Lobo- benthic macroinvertebrate analysis (UFJF); Rodrigo Silva do Carmo – bird counts (CES); Frank van Oosterhout- ntlectual support (WUR).

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LIMNOLOGY AROUND THE WORLD: POLAND

The Limnological Station of the University of Gdańsk with a Mission to Monitor and Protect Water

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The Limnological Station of the University of Gdańsk was established in 1959 on Raduńskie Górne Lake in upper Radunia River System at the Kashubian Lake District (Fig.1; Lange, 2005). The physical and geographical diversity of the area, *i.e.*, the multitude of morphological forms, lithological diversity of surface sediments, specific climatic and hydrographic conditions make this place a great opportunity to conduct scientific research. The Station also carries out didactic tasks related to field classes in topography, meteorology, geomorphology and hydrology.

Fig. 1 Opening ceremony of the Limnological Station in 1959 (Photo by J. Szukalski)

The Radunia basin, where the Limnological Station is located, is drained by a unique system of cascading lakes, forming the so-called “Raduńskie Lakes Circle” (Fig. 2; Bajkiewicz-Grabowska, 2007). In addition, meteorological observations according to the KLIMAT standard and evaporation measurements are also carried out (Miętus, 2006). These data form the basis for the development of climatological maps for Poland for multi-year periods. The maps are also transmitted to the Regional Climatology Centre in Offenbach, Germany. Components of the radiation balance are performed as part of the Polish AOD network (Markowicz *et al.*, 2021).

These unique water resources, along with climate research in collaboration with the Institute of Meteorology and Water Management, are not only valuable scientific data but also educational and training tools. The diverse morphology of these lakes allows a detailed analysis of different types of seasonal and vertical stratification patterns of temperature and oxygen. This and other physio-chemical and biological parameters together with climatic data, all contribute to understanding the factors responsible for lake productivity, rate of organic matter transformation and carbon cycling.

The unfortunate increase in eutrophication in recent years due to climate change and anthropogenic pressure requires a holistic approach to protect these water resources. Lakes are one of the most beautiful gifts of nature, while at the same time presenting a huge challenge to keep them healthy for future generations, requiring close cooperation between all stakeholders. In this

Fig. 2 Map from Bajkiewicz-Grabowska, 2007. Localization of the Limnological Station (LS) at Raduńskie Górne Lake in Radunia Basin (Lakes: 1 - Stężycie, 2 - Raduńskie Górne, 3 - Raduńskie Dolne, 4 - Rekowo, 5 - Białe, 6 - Kłodno, 7 - Brodno Małe, 8 - Brodno Wielkie, 9 - Lubowisko, 10 - Dąbrowskie, 11 - Patulskie, 12 - Ostrzyckie, 13 - Bukrzyno Małe, 14 - Bukrzyno Wielkie, 15 - Kniewo, 16 - Zamkowisko, 17 - Stare Czaple, 18 - Kamionka, 19 - Sołeckie and 20 - Trzebnio)

situation, the mission of the Limnological Station, in addition to scientific research and educational activities, also needs to support the local community, water managers and politicians in the implementation of innovative monitoring programs.

Fig. 3 Top: Voluntary water monitoring (Photo by R. Gluszewski); bottom: Conference and workshop “What can we do for Kashubian lakes?” organized for local authorities, water managers and the local community (Photo by K. Legeżyńska)

The creation of an integrated and effective educational and training program at the Limnological Station gives a real chance to understand how aquatic ecosystems function, and thus protect them. An important element of the Station’s activity are projects involving the public in Citizen Science initiatives. Starting from voluntary water monitoring with scientists, specialized training, to expert support for the implementation of bottom-up initiatives for the protection and restoration of lakes (Fig. 3).

Fig. 4 Installation of floating islands demonstration

Fig. 5 Applied practical field and laboratory training in ecohydrology for international students. (Photos by J. Dunalska)

The advantage of activities carried out at the Station is not only the possibility of transferring theoretical knowledge, but also its practical application. For this purpose, prototypes of Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) methods used in water protection are being created at the Station (Fig. 4). Demonstrations of individual solutions on a semi-technical and technical scale with additional on-site explanations give great training and educational opportunities for a wide range of stakeholders (school children, students, local government officials, water managers and users).

The uniqueness of the Limnological Station comes from its location and innovative teaching methods both in Polish and English means that it can be an important scientific, educational and training center not only for stakeholders in Poland but also for guests from Europe and the world (Fig. 5). [Find out more here.](#)

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*The Limnological Station of the University of Gdańsk on Raduńskie Górne Lake at the Kashubian Lake District.
Photo by Błażej Zablotny.*

LIMNOLOGY AROUND THE WORLD: UNITED STATES

The Conference of the Lakes: Art and science come together to highlight threats to lakes around the world.

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“What are the sciences? Only categories for thinking. Sciences can be taught separately, but they can’t be used separately, either for seeing land or doing anything with it. What is art? Only the drama of the land’s working.”

Aldo Leopold, North American Wildlife Conference 1942

“If you’ve seen one lake, you’ve seen one lake.”

A phrase heard often at a Global Lake Ecological Observatory Network (GLEON) meeting

Art is a valuable tool to connect science to the broader public. Science-art collaborations can effectively transmit concepts and reshape misconceptions (Arce-Nazario, 2016). Art acts as a framework for visual and social experiences, which can create empathy towards the natural environment and generate appreciation (Marks *et al.*, 2016). These emotional and aesthetic connections can make people more willing to invest in conserving what they appreciate and value (Curtis, 2009). In many ways, science and art are not that different from each other. Science itself is a creative process, and historically co-production in science and art was more common (*e.g.*, Leonardo da Vinci; Solina, 2022). Recent studies have found similarities in the thought processes and habitats used in art and science (Root-Bernstein *et al.*, 2019; Scheffer *et al.*, 2017), as well as correlations between art practices and scientific achievement (Root-Bernstein *et al.*, 2019).

Here we describe a science-art collaboration that highlights the issues lakes face across the world, through creating ‘portraits’ of each lake. Catherine O’Reilly and Alice Hargrave worked together to create artwork using datasets from various lakes, including at least one from each continent (cover photo, Fig.1). Many of these datasets were gathered from members of Global Lake Ecological Observatory Network (GLEON) after Hargrave and O’Reilly attended the 2019 annual meeting. Once lakes and datasets were selected, Hargrave and O’Reilly talked to researchers who studied those lakes to learn more about the broader context. In addition, Hargrave

did a 1-month residency at Flathead Lake Biological Station, which allowed her to work with aquatic scientists, go sampling on the lake, and have time to immerse herself in creating the artwork. Funding for this project came from The Andy Warhol Foundation for the Visual Arts through a grant written by Kendra Paitz, Director and Chief Curator at University Galleries of Illinois State University.

Each ‘lake portrait’ is based on the patterns of the scientific data from that lake. The artwork incorporates published or unpublished data that describes the environmental issue for that lake. Hargrave often used the original colors from the scientific figure, as in her world of photography she wanted to keep an element of truth in the work despite the fact that colors in the data are simply random unlike the dictum in art that she follows of “form follows function” — that there should be a reason for every color choice in the art, even if it is a due to subjective emotional expression. Each “lake portrait” is a unique pattern created with diverse source material—the data, vintage photos associated with the lake, and photos Hargrave was able to make, often using colors of the water itself, including underwater photography. Printed on semi-transparent fabric, a lake portrait is 3 meters tall and 1.5 m wide, and is typically hung with other lake portraits in a multi-layered installation, echoing the idea of a conference of interconnected waters. Initially, 20 lakes were done, representing each of the seven continents (Table 1), and we continue to expand to other lakes. These lakes also represent a range of climate change influences. Some lakes are warming, some lakes are drying up, and some lakes are being born as glaciers melt. Other lakes are experiencing changes in their chemistry, species compositions, and food web dynamics.

The collection of pieces is titled *The Conference of the Lakes*, in reference to Farid ud-Din Attar’s 12th-century poem, *The Conference of the Birds*. This poem alludes to the challenging journey taken to reach enlightenment, along with the excuses that hinder progress - in much the same way humanity has been making excuses for not tackling the climate crises. The poem also underscores ideas of individuality that are reflected in each lake’s individual portrait. Incorporated into the story is the idea that people do have the ability to evolve, and that the journey can be one of success if surmounted as a group (*e.g.*, a conference) rather than by individuals with selfish, short-sighted goals. The title is also an allusion to the gathering of scientists at their own conferences.

The collection and individual lake portraits have been shown at multiple exhibitions. The premiere exhibition opened in March 2021 at the University Galleries, Illinois State University, as part of *Alice Hargrave: The Canary in the Lake* (Figs. 2, 3). The exhibition ran for three months and also included real-time virtual tours that created the 3-dimensional experience of walking among the lakes. These virtual tours allowed people from around the USA and other countries to view the exhibition. Faculty from science and non-science courses integrated the exhibition into their curriculum. The collaborators participated virtually in class visits and tours, which allowed Hargrave to describe her process and O’Reilly to explain the environmental impacts. [This exhibition is available online](#) as part of the 2021 archives. The online material includes photos and video as well as extensive information that describes each lake portrait in more detail, including the sources of the data and citations for scientific papers about each lake. Over the last year, pieces have also been shown in five other galleries and cultural centers in Virginia, Illinois, Montana, and New York.

Fig. 1 A partial view of the installation *The Conference of the Lakes after Farid Attar*, in University Galleries at Illinois State University, USA, 2021. Each lake ‘portrait’ is printed on a large fabric piece that hangs from the ceiling, with 11 portraits visible here. The colors on the lake portraits are often taken from photos of the lakes, and the patterns are taken from datasets, in some cases with other images related to the lake being incorporated into the piece as well. Altogether, the portraits highlight the diversity of lakes, how unique each lake is, and the range of environmental issues faced by lakes around the world.

Photo by M. Hassel, University Galleries.

Fig. 2 In the background between two hanging lake portraits is another installation by Alice Hargrave titled Herbarium, lake algae, macrophytes, 2020-2021. This work is 29 pigment prints photographed from the collection of the Flathead Lake Biological Station in Montana, USA.

Fig. 3 A visitor is seen through a lake portrait, highlighting their transparent nature. The ability to wander among the hanging portraits reflects the three-dimensional nature of lakes themselves. Photo by M. Hassel, University Galleries.

What do Hargrave and O'Reilly hope the public gains from viewing this artwork? One of the goals for this exhibition was to help audiences recognize how unique each lake is, by offering an experiential engagement that visualizes what is often invisible. Ultimately, the idea was to create a space that helps people move beyond the 2-dimensional surface of a lake, to appreciate the complexity that exists below the surface and within a landscape and historical context. One visitor instantly started twirling and dancing through the hanging fabrics, and another instinctively reached out to touch them (they are touchable!). Although each lake portrait reflects different environmental stressors and impacts, this more detailed information requires reading the titles and/or other contextual information offered on wall text and online. Even if visitors walk out only reflecting on the idea that lakes are unique and are being affected by change, that's a successful step in helping people appreciate their world and hopefully be more willing to enact change.

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Table 1. List of existing lake portraits - *The Conference of the Lakes, after Farid Attar* - solvent prints on fabric of lake portraits
3 m x 1.5 m ea. 2020 - 2021

Panel	Lake	Country	Issue
1	Lake Baikal	Russia	warming
2	Lake Tanganyika	Tanzania	warming, fish loss
3	Lake Vanda	Antarctica	growing lake, ice melt
4	Lake Hillier	Australia	genome of <i>S. ruber</i> , pink lake
5	Lake Tovel	Italy	warming
6	Lake Zigadenus	Canada	decreasing turbidity "Losing Blue"
7	The Loch & Sky Pond	Colorado, USA	atmospheric nitrogen deposition
8	Lake Tahoe	USA	decreasing clarity
9	Lake Otsego	New York, USA	warming, invasive species
10	Lake Tovel	Italy	magenta algal bloom loss
11	Northern Wisconsin Lakes	USA	mercury
12	Lake Superior	USA	ice loss
13	Lake Abiyata	Ethiopia	shrinking lake, habitat loss
14	Lakes Mendota, Menona, and Wingra	Wisconsin, USA	rising salinity
15	Lake Milford	Kansas, USA	toxic algal blooms
16	Lake Thingvallvatn	Iceland	ice loss, finger rafting
17	Lake Escanaba, Wisconsin	USA	phenological whiplash
18	Lake Blavatn	Iceland	new lake, glacier extinction
19	El Morado Proglacial Lake	Chile	new lake before green
20	Flathead Lake	Montana, USA	invasive species and mercury in the food chain

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ANDREA PATRICIA GUZMÁN ARIAS | COLOMBIA

I became interested in limnology during my Bachelor's degree in Biology in Colombia, where I had the opportunity to learn about different aquatic systems during my fieldwork. I am currently a third-year Ph.D. student at the National Autonomous University of Mexico. My main research interests are greenhouse gases (GHG) in tropical and temperate lakes. I am particularly interested in understanding the anaerobic oxidation of methane coupled to denitrification (DAMO) in lakes. High nitrate concentrations and elevated methane emissions severely affect the functional role of lakes, worldwide. The coupling of the processes of anaerobic oxidation of methane and denitrification can alleviate the contribution of lakes to global change and help its mitigation, but we still do not know much about its controlling mechanism.

Colombia and Mexico are countries with exceptional natural wealth but with many environmental problems. One of them is the eutrophication of freshwater ecosystems. Therefore, my second goal is to actively interact with the communities surrounding the lakes in order to make them aware of my work and engage them to become part of the conservation or recovery of their waterbodies.

As a new member of SIL I feel honored to highlight my studies within my research group and I appreciate the work done by SIL to disseminate and publicize new contributions of researchers in epicontinental aquatic systems around the world.

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RAEL ADHIAMBO | KENYA

I am currently in my third year of studies undertaking a Ph.D. in oceanography and limnology under the African Centre of Excellence in Coastal Resilience at the University of Cape Coast in Ghana. My research focuses on understanding the multiple impacts of climate change and pollution in tropical estuaries. These ecosystems are currently facing multiple and cumulative impacts from anthropogenically driven environmental stressors (*i.e.*, pollution and climate change) that work in tandem to affect their structure and functioning. I am particularly interested in how plankton communities respond to both the individual and combined impacts of climate change at the functional and molecular levels. This research has been necessitated by the general lack of knowledge on the impact of both climate change and pollution on the productivity of coastal ecosystems. In addition, there are existing gaps in knowledge on the impact of climate change stressors such as warming on tropical aquatic microorganisms or how stressors modulate the impacts of pollution. It is therefore envisaged that the results of this study will support effective estuarine management and decision-making and build on the already existing efforts at national, regional, and global levels to combat climate change and pollution.

Since joining SIL, I have been deeply inspired and motivated by the existing pool of expertise, knowledge, and resources that the association directs toward the development of limnology research. Through SIL, I have also been fortunate enough to receive the Tonolli Memorial Fund which is awarded to inspiring individual limnologists of developing countries. I look forward to participating in more SIL activities and meetings and taking advantage of the benefits and mentorship that come from it.

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MICHIO KUMAGAI | JAPAN

Earlier in my career, I organized BITEX'93 (Biwa-ko Transport Experiment), a limnological research collaboration at Lake Biwa, Japan, that involved 165 people including scientists, engineers and students from nine countries. Since that time, I have devoted myself to studies at Lake Biwa using advanced technologies such as AUVs (Autonomous Underwater Vehicles). This was a unique approach in early 2000s, because AUVs were not commercially available at that time for monitoring lakes as well as oceans. We have obtained extensive AUV imagery of the benthic ecosystem of Lake Biwa from 2000 to 2022, and this has revealed dramatic changes in the diversity of endemic animals, likely due to climate change and lake warming. Recently, I began an international research program at Lake Biwa and Lake Kinneret entitled "Advanced ICT (Information and Communication Technology) for monitoring freshwater ecosystem resilience", which aims at developing a new information network to monitor the early stages of cyanobacterial blooms. In 2016, I initiated an education program on lake science for junior students from 10 to 18 years old, and two of these young students gave oral presentations at SIL2022 in Berlin. The aim of this program is to foster exchange between junior and senior limnologists. SIL is one of most suitable organizations to provide such precious opportunities to young people who are eager to learn and contribute to the environmental sciences, and to train for future careers that address the pressing challenges of global climate change.

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BENJAMIN MISTELI | SWITZERLAND

I am currently at the end of my PhD studies at the University of Rennes 1 (France). My work mainly focuses on understanding how invasive macrophytes influence phytoplankton, zooplankton and macroinvertebrates living around them and how the removal of macrophytes influences these communities. I became interested in freshwater ecology during the first research project during my Bachelor's, in which I compared macroinvertebrates from an alpine spring with those from a nearby river. Following that, I wrote my Bachelor's and Master's thesis about environmental impacts on macroinvertebrates communities in different systems. Working on my Master's studies as a research assistant at EAWAG (Switzerland) for 1.5 years inspired me to continue my adventure in Limnology and to pursue a PhD. Here I am, three years later, finishing up my PhD and I have collected many valuable experiences on the way. SIL has played an important role at this last stage of my PhD in different ways. Since summer 2021, I've become an associate editor in training for Inland Waters, a great opportunity for early career researchers like me to learn how editorship functions. Thanks to the Robert G. Wetzel Memorial Travel Award, I could travel to the SIL100 in Berlin. Listening to many interesting talks, talking with old friends, meeting new colleagues and being part of this community were great motivations for me in this tough last half year of my PhD. Thank you SIL for all the support for ECRs. I am glad to be part of SIL.

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Obituary

Brian Robert Allanson
1928 – 2022

Brian Allanson (along with a twin sister) was born in Colombo, Sri Lanka on 1 January 1928, where their father worked as a marine engineer. Following medical advice to move to a 'healthier climate', the family returned to the United Kingdom shortly thereafter. A decade later, Brian's father got a job in Port Elizabeth (South Africa). Thus started (what became) 'Neptune Engineering' – a marine engineering enterprise, active in the recovery of many ships damaged on the dangerous route round the Cape following the subsequent start of World War II.

Brian was schooled at Grey High School in Port Elizabeth (now Gqeberha), demonstrating a passionate interest in the sciences at a young age. He was always dissecting rabbits, rats and other creatures – nearly driving his mother mad. Brian's father persuaded a very well-trained Welsh chemist (Jimmy James) working in the city to take on the young schoolboy as a pupil. Brian recalled Jimmy as an extraordinary teacher, who facilitated Brian's completion of the equivalent of university first year level Chemistry while he was writing his matric.

His tertiary studies commenced at the University of Natal in Pietermaritzburg, from which he qualified in Zoology and Chemistry in 1948. He recalled the often-oppressive heat of cycling the mile or so to and from the barracks-like living quarters of Oribi Village, which served as the university 'student residence' at the time. After graduating, he accepted an assistant Science-master post at Hilton College, which he held for three years before moving to the University of Cape Town (UCT), from which he graduated with an MSc in Marine Biology in 1954. In 1955, he was appointed as a Junior Lecturer in UCT's Zoology department, headed by Prof. John Day, and married Sue Nicholson, who was studying Librarianship at UCT.

In 1956, Brian accepted a four-year long Transvaal River Research Fellowship award from the South African Council for Scientific and Industrial Research (CSIR) and the Transvaal Provincial Administration, to determine the health of the rivers feeding the water supply of the province. The couple moved to Pretoria in Transvaal (now Gauteng) – marking the beginning of Brian's subsequent illustrious career in limnology. During tenure of this fellowship, Brian was sent to England for a year as a visiting worker at the DSIR Water Pollution Laboratories in Stevenage, Hertfordshire, where he completed the write-up for his studies of the province's polluted waters for a PhD

from UCT. On his return, he was appointed Head of the Division of Hydrobiology at the CSIR's National Institute for Water Research, where he continued work on rivers and reservoirs, undertaking seminal work on Hartbeespoort Dam, the river reservoir subsequently infamous for its severe hypertrophy. Notably, Brian's studies here were a sequel of sorts to preceding work on this man-made lake by G.E. Hutchinson.

In 1963, Brian was appointed Professor and Head of the Department of Zoology and Entomology at Rhodes University (in Grahamstown, now Makhanda) – the youngest Professor ever to have been appointed there. The arrival of this dashing young Professor reportedly caused quite a stir on campus. Brian was of physically imposing stature, with a full head of silver-white hair (acquired in his young twenties as a genetic inheritance) rendering him an intimidating character who later became surreptitiously called the 'Great White Shark'. This persona stood him in good stead in later years when working as an environmental consultant! Grahamstown became the Allanson family home for 25 years where they firstly lived in 'the Hermitage', an imposing old home in the town, and thereafter on a small farm on the outskirts of the town. Their five children (Robyn, Elizabeth, twins Nicolas and Sally, and Peter) grew up and were schooled in this small university town.

As Professor of Zoology and Entomology, Brian continued his hydrobiological and limnological research endeavours, and giving strong encouragement to graduate work in estuaries. However, his academic diversity and versatility quickly became evident as he supervised scores of MSc and PhD student researchers on a wide range of taxa (including annelids, insects, molluscs, crustaceans, arachnids, fish, birds and mammals) in single-species autecological studies through multispecies synecology (phytoplankton, zooplankton, zoobenthos, hydrophyte and microbial communities) to whole ecosystems. His aquatic research interests spanned both inland waters (rivers, coastal lakes, reservoirs, wetlands) and thalassic systems (estuaries, nearshore coastal zones, later extending to open ocean waters.) Many of his graduates subsequently gained strong scientific reputations and prominence for their expertise. Brian followed academic interests on a variety of topics. In many ways, he was the personification of a classical English professor, with research interests and endeavours spanning a diversity of topics.

Indeed, holistic vision was a predominant hallmark of Brian, who exemplified Macfadyen's (Macfadyen, A. 1957. *Animal ecology: Aims and methods*. Pitman, London) definition of an ecologist as "*something of a chartered libertine [who] roams at will over the preserves of the plant and animal biologist, the physiologist, the meteorologist, the geologist, the physicist, the chemist, and even the sociobiologist [and] poaches from all these and from other established and respected disciplines.*" Perhaps understandable at that time, Brian's engagement in cross- and inter-disciplinary research – with studies involving plants (Botany) or microbes (Microbiology) – led to concern within certain other departments in the university about encroachment threats – Macfadyenian poaching.

In 1965, Brian established the Institute for Fresh Water Studies (IFWS) at Rhodes, serving as its first Director. The IFWS played a seminal role in the investigation of the physics, chemistry and biology of natural coastal

lakes both in KwaZulu-Natal (Lake Sibaya and the Kosi Bay lakes/estuarine system) and the Southern Cape (Swartvlei and associated Wilderness lakes system). Brian master-minded the construction of permanent field stations on L. Sibaya, and subsequently on Swartvlei. His active research on L. Sibaya necessitated a twice-yearly two-day drive from Grahamstown. Arriving at the lake, Brian would customarily perform what was, to the student entourage, an almost sacrilegious waste: at dusk, he would walk to the end of the mooring jetty to pour some bottled beer on the lake as a '*libation to the gods*' – to ensure safety and success for the venture and all its participants. It certainly worked on the first count – safety: despite research thrusts that required scuba-diving in the crocodile and hippo-inhabited lake, no-one was ever lost or injured at the field station. However, rising lake levels resulting from cyclical climate-pattern events did flood the Sibaya field station, forcing its abandonment in the late 1970's.

Brian's own research interests on L. Sibaya became dominated by what was a resource-constrained pre-occupation/obsession with 'physical limnology', especially the Wedderburn lake number. In due course, this led to his interactions with Jörg Imberger and John C Patterson at the Centre for Water Research, University of Western Australia. His plexiglass model lake constructed to visually demonstrate the establishment of thermal stratification, wind-induced mixing, and 'overturn' strongly augmented the persuasive and compelling case Brian made to a prominent leading bank for the endowment of a specialized chair at Rhodes – the Barclays National Bank Chair of Postgraduate Limnology. RCH recalls making special arrangements to ensure that this contraption could be carried as 'cabin-luggage' for a flight to Johannesburg for a pivotal meeting that secured this endowment. During its 5-year term (1983 – 1987), this endowed chair, held by RCH, facilitated the completion of some 15 MSc (Limnology) graduates. Brian was instrumental in further capitalizing on the educational value of the chair through its support of short specialized courses run by notable experts – including Clifford Mortimer (physical limnology) and Brian Moss (algal biology).

Following loss of the Sibaya station, the focus of its IFWS researchers was redirected to the Vanderkloof (formerly P.K. le Roux) Dam – one of SA's largest and most turbid impoundments. While this reservoir on the Orange River was considerably closer to Rhodes than Sibaya (an eight-hour rather than a two-day drive each way), Brian's active research thereon was increasingly time-constrained. Ever resourceful, he trained for a Private Pilot's License, thereafter buying himself a Piper Cherokee (ZS-EOD) and flying himself to an airfield near Lake le Roux. Brian flew for ten years, finding the experience exciting, at least when weather was not challenging. He suggested RCH pursue a parallel path – no persuasion needed – leading to their sharing of many research-purposed flights.

During his tenure as Professor at Rhodes, Allanson had spells as visiting professor and/or researcher at Indiana University, Oxford University and at the FBA's Ferry House, Windermere. He further collaborated on an on-going basis with the Water Research Centre at the University of Western Australia.

Brian was a stickler for discipline and appropriate protocol, accepting only rigorous excellence from his

students, who otherwise risked comments like “poorly understood regurgitated undergraduate nonsense”. This was particularly intimidating for younger students. Dress codes had to be maintained – bare feet were definitively ‘out’. By consistent example, he showed the importance of ‘*Doing the right thing, and doing it properly*’, and ‘*not spoiling the ship for a happpence* [Brian’s modification of *ha’p’orth*] of tar’.

Brian was not without detractors. Certain mannerisms borne of his British heritage – “*My dear fellow...*” were (mis)perceived by some as pompous arrogance. On his first meeting with Brian (November 1970), RDR, dressed in jeans and a t-shirt, recalls that Brian came out of his office dressed in a suit and tie and in a loud voice said, “*My dear fellow, welcome.*” Some who witnessed this meeting were left wondering how long this jaunty north American would survive in Brian’s realm: The giant’s bite was obviously more forgiving than his bark.

As a determined man of resolute principle, Brian’s deeply held convictions of right and wrong could be (and were) interpreted in a negative light by some, particularly since the ‘landscape’ of limnological endeavour in South Africa was (and remains) severely under-resourced and resultingly fractious – even ‘toxic’ in the words of one practitioner. However, those who knew Brian recognized that he was driven to ensure the honest pursuit of evidence-based hard science, with no attempts at personal aggrandizement.

While not explicitly articulating negativity about the national limnological arena, Brian voted with his feet – increasingly aligning himself with its friendlier and better-resourced marine counterparts. Already well-established in the estuarine arena, he began venturing into deeper offshore waters by exploiting cruises of the SA Agulhas – the SA supply ship that re-provisions and relieves the manned SANAE base in Antarctica and Marion Island – as ‘*voyages of scientific opportunity*’. Ship-based scientific teams (of multi-institutional origin) making these voyages conducted research on ocean temperatures, chemistry, plankton and primary productivity, alongside studies of atmospheric physics, and marine birds and mammals. Brian himself served as Chief Scientist aboard two relief voyages to Antarctica, firstly in 1981 (when RCH was also aboard), and a cruise to Marion Island. During these voyages, Brian shared his broad knowledge liberally. These were preludes to his establishment in 1983 of the Southern Ocean Research Group – a highly collaborative endeavour that remains active to this day.

Brian Allanson formally retired from the Chair of Zoology at Rhodes in 1988, but continued to serve the University as a researcher and mentor of singular distinction. During his long tenure as Chair, he provided very distinguished service to the university. *Inter alia*, he served as Dean of the Faculty of Science for several terms, as Chairman of the Research Committee, and as the first Dean of Research. To honour this contribution, his students, colleagues and others set up the Prof BR Allanson Scholarship for post-doctoral study. His scientific involvements outside the ambit of the university itself were both numerous and influential. Brian was the first Vice President of the Limnological Society of Southern Africa (LSSA) when it was founded in 1963, and President in 1970. He also served as President of the Zoological Society of Southern Africa (ZSSA) for two terms (1986 and 1988.) He was chairman and/or active participant member of

many and various national scientific working groups.

Brian and Sue retired to Knysna, where Brian established a small practice as a consulting aquatic ecologist. With many Knysna residents concerned that the Knysna estuary was ‘dying’, Brian was asked to survey it. From the resulting evidence-based hard science, the estuary was instead shown to be in good health, despite facing a range of potential threats. To mitigate these, Brian set up the Knysna Basin Project in 1995. This was a locally- and corporate-sponsored research programme to monitor and assess the environmental condition, and safeguard the holistic health of the Knysna estuary, known as South Africa’s most bio-diverse estuary and home to a number of rare and endangered species – notably a species of sea-horse. ‘Basin’ in the title of this project reflected Brian’s long-standing recognition of the importance of the catchment management on the environmental health of any basin’s aquatic systems – the ‘stream and valley’ concept expounded in a SIL Edgardo Baldi

Photo credit: www.leisureisleknysna.co.za

Memorial lecture (Hynes, HBN. 1975. The stream and its valley. *Verh. Internat. Verein. Limnol.* 19: 1-15).

Brian was a prolific researcher, a much-valued teacher and postgraduate supervisor, and an inspiration to all who followed in the directions that he opened up. During the course of his long career, he published over 100 scholarly journal articles and many reports, conference proceedings and four books which he co-authored or edited. As an inspirational and extraordinary example of determined and persistent scholarship, he published a journal article and saw the graduation of his last PhD candidate at the age of 90. He received many honours and awards, having been inducted as a Fellow of the Royal Society of South Africa (1968), recipient of the first LSSA gold medal (in the late 1980’s) and the ZSSA’s 13th Gold Medal (1987), Doctor of Science from the University of Natal (1980), and South Africa’s Order of Meritorious Service – Silver – awarded by South Africa’s State President for services to Science and University Education (1990), and Doctor of Science *Honoris Causa* from Rhodes University (1992). In 2010, his outstanding achievements culminated in the award of SIL’s Naumann-Thienemann Medal – the highest honour bestowed internationally for outstanding scientific

contributions to limnology – for his leadership of the development of limnology in South Africa.

On a personal/private front, Brian will be remembered as a committed Rotarian, with certain musical aptitudes – a good singing voice in Grahamstown’s local choir and some penchant for piano-tinkering. He enjoyed sailing, even building his own dinghies with friends and sons. While none of his children followed a scientific path, shortly before he died, he was delighted to be able to attend the graduation of one of his grandsons, with a degree in Oceanography from UCT.

Authors of this obituary (RCH, RDR) were PhD students supervised by Brian Allanson, and are the last surviving co-authors of the 1990 treatise on southern African inland waters (Allanson *et al.*, 1990).

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RDR: Richard D Roberts,
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Canada

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